

AWARE2ALL

D3.2 In-cabin integration of OMS technologies and components

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About AWARE2ALL

Facing to the challenge of future highly automated vehicles, where occupants can freely orient themselves to engage in non-driving activities. This new environment prompts questions about how car occupants will actually sit, what activities they will engage in, and how they will be informed through the HMI to keep them in the loop if necessary.

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) deployment in traffic, by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and changes in the interaction of different road users caused by the emergence of HAV through the development of innovative technologies along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies.

AWARE2ALL will develop safety and HMI systems that will be interrelated through achieving a holistic understanding of the scene to ensure safe operation of the HAV. AWARE2ALL proposes a common conceptual universal safety framework for considering Human Machine Interaction (HMI). The project will be built on the results of projects funded under H2020 and other R&D programmes addressing the identification of new safety-critical situations and the most likely positions and postures considering the expected HAV applications.

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

AWARE2ALL includes 16 partners from 6 EU Member States (ES, DE, GR, NL, FR and SE) and 2 associated countries (TR, CS) and it is complemented by the International Advisory Board (IAB) representing key stakeholders that covers the full research and industrial development automotive value chain, more specifically in the CCAM field.

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Executive Summary

One of the key technologies developed in Aware2All is advanced Occupant Monitoring Systems (OMS) for in-cabin monitoring. Its primary objective is to enhance safety and comfort for all vehicle occupants. These OMS make the measurement, modelling and assessment of the driver state primely and occupant state secondly related to visual and cognitive distraction, situation awareness, and health, among others. Different unobtrusive monitoring devices that capture multi-modal data are used. This data enters algorithms that use deep learning inference methods to extract gaze direction, body pose, etc. Various types of sensors that capture different type of information are used and explained here. The software and hardware necessary to build and implement the prototypes is explained in the following pages.

During the execution of WP3 (Occupant monitoring and iHMI solutions), the algorithms, data and sensors were defined. One outcome of this work package is the set of OMS technologies and prototypes developed and integrated by each partner.

These technologies were integrated into several testing facilities for system verification. An additional integration effort of some of the algorithms exposed here was performed in collaboration with partners of Aware2All building Demonstrator 3, where the testing facility was the driving simulator prepared by IRSTX.

In this document, the description of the developed OMS prototypes and their implementation into the different testing facilities are presented. More details regarding performance metrics or integration in Demo 3, can be found in D3.4.

Acronyms and terms

Acronym	Term
AD	Autonomous Driving
Aoi	Area / Region of Interest
DM	Decision-Making
DMS	Driver Monitoring System
EEG	Electroencephalogram
F-CRS	Front Child Restraint System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HOD	HandsOn Detection
ID	Driver identifier
IR	Infrared
KPD	KeyPoint Detection
ML	Machine Learning
LiDAR	Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging
OMS	Occupant Monitoring System
R-CRS	Rear Child Restraint System
RA	Risk Assessment
SA	Situational Awareness
R-CRS	Rear Child Restraint System
SAGAT	Situation Awareness Global Assessment Technique
SOC	Seat Occupancy Classification

SOD	Seat Occupancy Detection
TOR	TakeOver Request
TTO	Time to TakeOver
ToC	Transition of Control
iHMI	Internal Human-Machine Interface

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

This document is the written form of deliverable D3.2, which is of type DEMO, under the nomenclature of Europe deliverable types: D3.2 is, under this understanding, a set of integrated prototypes of OMS technologies, developed in WP3. This document summarizes the main features of these prototypes and will be uploaded to the EC platform to acknowledge the production of D3.2, which can be showcased or demonstrated at the locations where the integrated prototypes exist.

This deliverable shows the prototypes developed in Aware2All regarding Occupant Monitoring Systems (OMS) technologies. There are multiple contents and visual support that can help describe the functioning and the implementation of the prototypes into different facilities.

This deliverable is highly related to:

- **D3.1 Occupant state and behaviour analysis and iHMI.** There, the technologies implemented here were explained. More scientific and detailed description is included in D3.1. This deliverable is due to M19 (May 2024) and is classified as sensitive.
- **D3.3. Cognitive empathic HMI design and implementation.** The current D3.2 only describes the OMS algorithms, please refer to D3.3 to read about Internal Human-Machine Interface (iHMI), also developed in WP3. This deliverable is due to M28 (Feb 2025) and is classified as public.
- **D3.4. Test results and final design and implementation.** The technologies and algorithms presented here are verified and some were jointly integrated into a demonstrator for user testing. The performance metrics and integration details can be found in D3.4.
- **D2.1 AWARE2ALL Systems requirements.** This is a description of refined use cases and based on that, the requirements for the system as well as the detailed test scenarios for demonstrators. This deliverable is due to M12 (October 2023) and is classified as sensitive.

This deliverable contains a set of algorithms developed in WP3 and provides detailed insights into their functioning and integration.

1.2. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D3.2 is public. Primarily, this document intends to showcase the prototypes developed during the Aware2All project regarding OMS. It shows different partners developments, implementations in testing facilities and technological achievements. The main intended audience of this document is people with a technological and automotive industry background, but anyone interested in the project and its outcomes is welcome to read this document.

2. OMS Prototypes

This section describes the overview of the Aware2All OMS prototypes as individual components and their individual integration processes. Each sub-section obeys to a single module or algorithm that was integrated alone or with other modules into a testing platform (vehicles, computing hardware, etc.), consuming inputs from a set of sensors (Cameras RGB, IR, depth sensors, etc.) and giving an output.

2.1. Driver Identification

The driver identification system, as described in D3.1, is a software module that re-identifies a driver previously registered in a database. Within Aware2All project, this module will provide the identification (ID) of the driver to other modules to support personalization of comfort and communication systems. This system is implemented in VICOMTECH's test vehicle as will be described in 1.1.3.

The system consists of a face detection algorithm that provides the crop of the image where a face is detected. This crop is sent to the re-identification system that extracts key information from the face and compares this with the ones registered in the database. If there is a match, the correspondent ID is returned. If the driver is not already included in the database, it will be tagged as unknown.

For the registration of the driver, it is necessary to capture three images of the person that are different from each other and he/she will be saved with an ID (that doesn't have to be the driver's name for privacy reasons). A menu will appear to register the new identity or to delete an existing one. This menu is shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. SYSTEM MENU TO ADD OR DELETE ENTRIES IN THE DATABASE

The system implements an IR modality to be able to be robust against low light environments. In Figure 2, the example visualization of the re-identification of the driver with ID 1 is presented in a real car context, in RGB and IR modality.

FIGURE 2. EXAMPLE OF VISUALIZATION OF THE DRIVERID SYSTEM (RGB AND IR MODALITIES)

1.1.1 Sensors

As mentioned, the system integrates sensors to process both RGB and IR images, allowing it to adapt to various lighting conditions, including low-light environments. The integration of these two sensors enhances the system's versatility and accuracy.

For the Driver ID system and the Gaze Estimation system, we employed an Intel RealSense D415 camera. This camera was strategically placed on the cockpit of the car in such a way that the driver's face is clearly visible, as shown in Figure 3. However, it's worth noting that there can be some interference or occlusion caused by the driver's hands on the steering wheel from this position.

FIGURE 3. INTEL REALSENSE D435 AND REALSENSE D415 CAMERAS

To address the need for Distraction Detection, we used an Intel RealSense D435 camera¹. This camera was mounted on the top of the A-pillar inside the car, pointing at the driver's body. This side view captures most of the driver's posture and is instrumental in identifying distractions. The placement of the cameras inside the vehicle is illustrated in Figure 4.

¹[Depth Camera D435 – Intel® RealSense™ Depth and Tracking Cameras](https://www.intelrealsense.com/depth-camera-d435/)
<https://www.intelrealsense.com/depth-camera-d435/>

FIGURE 4. DIAGRAM OF THE POSITION OF BODY AND FACE CAMERAS

1.1.2 RTMaps Diagram

The system is orchestrated using RTMaps software². This software can connect hardware, like cameras, and execute software components based on their input. This is mainly advantageous when multiple sensors and modules must work at the same time and/or have some dependencies between each other. The integrated systems with RTMaps are the Driver Identification, Driver Gaze Estimation and Driver Distraction Detection system. The RTMaps diagram created for the integration is shown in Figure 5.

There are dedicated RealSense modules in RTMaps that can be configured and read from the Intel RealSense Cameras presented in 1.1.1. Two of these modules were included to read D415 and D435 Intel cameras. A keyboard component is to handle the triggers for the Driver ID menu to register a new driver. Python bridge modules were included to execute Python scripts where the algorithms

² [RTMaps — Intempora](https://intempora.com/products/rmaps/) <https://intempora.com/products/rmaps/>

were programmed. Each Python bridge module represents an OMS system. Finally, the visual output is sent to three image viewer components that display different windows for each OMS system.

FIGURE 5 RTMAPS DIAGRAM

1.1.3 Test Vehicle

The integration of the Driver Identification, Driver Gaze Estimation and Driver Distraction Detection systems were performed in VICOMTECH’s test vehicle. This vehicle, shown in Figure 6, is a Toyota Prius 3rd generation.

FIGURE 6. VICOMTECH'S TEST VEHICLE

In its inside it is fully equipped with sensors and hardware to install many types of algorithms including OMS. For the Aware2All project, two of the three cameras for Driver monitoring were used.

2.2. Driver Gaze Estimation

The driver gaze estimation system, described in D3.1, is also implemented in the VICOMTECH's test vehicle described in 1.1.3. This system is a region-based gaze detector that identifies and outputs the specific region the driver is currently looking at. The system is designed to monitor nine distinct regions: the left, right, and center rear-view mirrors; the front; front right; left and right sides; the infotainment system; and the steering wheel.

2.2.1. Solution based on CNNs

The core of this algorithm consists of two main components: a face detector and an image classifier based on a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The face detector captures the face of the driver and returns a cropped image. This cropped image is then processed by the image classifier, which determines which of the nine regions the driver is looking at. This algorithm shares the same face detector module with the Driver ID system, demonstrating the efficient use of resources in our design.

To aid in visualization, we have designed a layout of the vehicle interior. The detected zone at any given moment is highlighted in yellow in this layout, providing a clear and intuitive representation of the driver's current focus as shown in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7. VISUALIZATION OF DRIVER GAZE ESTIMATION

2.2.2. Solution based on VLM's

With the introduction of new algorithms such as the Visual Language Models (VLM's) and their amazing zero-shot prediction capabilities, some tasks that require some analysis or reasoning for decision-making process may benefit from them. By integrating both visual and linguistic information, these models can go beyond simple labeling to generate detailed descriptions and provide answers to questions based on image analysis. Additionally, these models possess extensive knowledge about the world, enabling them to adapt to and consider situations that CNN's may not be able to handle. Additionally, this basic knowledge allows the model to learn tasks more efficiently, requiring less data compared to CNNs.

However, despite these advantages, gaze estimation, as approached above, can still be challenging without proper training. Throughout this project, the capabilities of VLMs in performing gaze estimation are thoroughly explored.

With the experimentation carried out, we found that for some state-of-the-art Visual Language Models (VLMs), identifying gaze direction was quite challenging. A set of experiments was defined to assess the required prior knowledge and abilities. The models tested were Llafix3-8B, Qwen2-VL-7B-Instruct and Llava1.5-13B. Through these experiments, we discovered that these models lack spatial reasoning and struggle to properly distinguish between right and left. As an example, in Figure 8, the model was asked if the driver is looking to their left. In Figure 9, the question was “Is the person looking to the right of the image?”.

FIGURE 8 QWEN'S PREDICTIONS TO TEXT PROMPT: IS THE PERSON LOOKING TO THEIR LEFT?

FIGURE 9 QWEN'S PREDICTIONS TO TEXT PROMPT: IS THE PERSON LOOKING TO THE RIGHT OF THE IMAGE?

For this problem, the image presented to the model is a frontal picture of the driver, meaning that the left of the image is the right of the driver. This inversion is particularly difficult for the VLMs to process. Additionally, the models struggled with the spatial knowledge of the car interior, such as the position of objects like the infotainment system and rear-view mirror.

To address these issues, we adapted the inference prompts to see if the results improved. With experiments like cropping, adding gaze vectors and arrows manually in the image like represented in Figure 10.

FIGURE 10 PROMPTING TECHNIQUES TO IMPROVE MODEL'S RESPONSE. CROPPING (LEFT), DRAWING GAZE VECTORS (CENTER), DRAWING ARROWS (RIGHT)

However, it was only after fine-tuning the model, taking into account the insights from our knowledge exploration, that the model could provide accurate predictions regarding the direction and the specific object inside the car that the driver was looking at, as shown in Figure 11.

The driver is looking to the right to check the side-view mirror

FIGURE 11 CORRECT RESPONSE OF THE MODEL AFTER FINE-TUNING

2.3. Driver Distraction Detection

The driver distraction detection system, as detailed in D3.1, is designed to assess drivers' distractions by detecting activities that imply distraction while driving. This system has been successfully implemented in the VICOMTECH test vehicle, described in 1.1.3 and utilizes the body-designated Intel RealSense D435 camera for image capture.

The core of this algorithm is an image classifier that processes the input image and classifies it into one of five categories: safe driving, texting (right hand), phone call (right hand), texting (left hand), and phone call (left hand). These categories represent actions that can cause cognitive, physical, and sometimes visual distractions. The distinction between right and left, is to have the information of which hand the driver is performing the distracting activity with.

To visualize the output of the distraction detection system, we developed a bar graph, as shown in Figure 12. Each bar corresponds to one of the five classes, and its fill level indicates the probability of that class. To ensure stability and avoid fluctuations in the predictions, the displayed probability is

calculated as an average of the last 20 frames. This approach provides a more stable and reliable prediction over time.

FIGURE 12. VISUALIZATION OF DISTRACTED DRIVER DETECTION SYSTEM

2.4. Stitching

The Aware2all imaging system by Gestigon is comprised of two wide-angle ToF (Time of Flight) cameras (see Figure 13). Even though each of them has quite a large field of view, a single camera cannot span the entire front row from the mounting location (rear view mirror). So two of them are required for both the driver (see Figure 15) and front passenger (see Figure 14) to be properly (i.e.: have the freedom to perform any action) imaged as a single image (see). Image stitching is implemented as a first module in overall software architecture and runs the ML algorithms of each of the following modules (KeyPoint Detection (KPD), SeatOccupancy Detection/Classification (SOD/SOC), HandsOn Detection (HOD) (see Figure 16) on a single stitched image, which corresponds to a virtual camera in the middle of the two physical ones. Also, 3D images can be stitched together (see Figure 18) to provide additional coordinates for airbag suppression.

FIGURE 13 TOF-CAMERA SETUP DEMO CAR

FIGURE 14 EXAMPLE OF SINGLE PASSENGER 2D IMAGE (CO-DRIVER)

FIGURE 15 EXAMPLE OF SINGLE PASSENGER 2D IMAGE (DRIVER)

FIGURE 16: EXAMPLE OF STITCHED 2D IMAGE BASED ON TWO SINGLE IMAGES

FIGURE 17 HIGH LEVEL SW-ARCHITECTURE

FIGURE 18 EXAMPLE OF 3D IMAGE STITCHING

2.5. 2D/3D Keypoint Detection

As planned in T3.1 the results (see: Figure 19 and Figure 20) of the Keypoint Detection are presented hereafter. These results are made using the existing YoloV7 model and by finetuning it with a dataset created by Gestigon.

The input frame consists of an image channel (2D IR and/or RGB) and a depth channel (if 3D required) of two synchronized ToF cameras. The output of the module are sets of 17 different keypoints, one set per individual. The keypoints are displayed for driver, co-driver and passengers on the back seat. The keypoints help to distinguish between torso, legs, forearms and face. By introducing a specific flag in the annotations, also occluded keypoints can be detected (see Figure 21). An occluded keypoint is a keypoint of a body joint, that can be estimated through context of the surrounding information, but is visibly occluded by any object or body part. Based on the stitched 3D images also 3D keypoints can be detected (see Figure 22)

FIGURE 19. EXAMPLE OF 2D KEYPOINT DETECTION

FIGURE 20: EXAMPLE OF 2D KEYPOINT DETECTION WITH CHILD

FIGURE 21 EXAMPLE OF OCCLUDED KEYPOINTS DETECTION

FIGURE 22 EXAMPLE OF 3D KEYPOINT DETECTION

2.6. Seat Occupancy Detection/Classification

As planned in T3.1 the results (see Figure 23) of Seat Occupancy Detection/Classification (SOD/SOC) are presented hereafter. These results are made using the existing YoloV7 model and by finetuning it with a dataset created by Gestigon.

The input frame consists of an image channel (2D IR and/or RGB). The output is a bounding box for all passengers (grey). It also provides a confidence level and the classification of adult or child (see Figure 24). Further outputs are bounding boxes for specific body segments and/or objects including the torso (yellow) and head (pink) as well as different types of child seats (violet for F-CRS). The child seat can be classified in four different types: booster, high back booster, front child restraint system (F-CRS) and rear child restraint system (R-CRS).

FIGURE 23: EXAMPLE OF SEAT OCCUPANCY DETECTION

FIGURE 24 EXAMPLE OF SEAT OCCUPANCY DETECTION WITH CHILD AND CHILD SEAT

2.7. HandsOn Detection

As planned in T3.1 the results (see Figure 26) of HandsOn are presented hereafter. These results are made using an existing ConvNeXt-ML Model and finetuning it on a dataset entirely created by Gestigon.

HandsOn Detection was implemented to detect whether the driver is in control of the car or not. The HandsOn Steering Wheel Detection system is a camera-based solution designed to monitor and ensure that at least one of the driver's hands is positioned on the steering wheel, ready to control the vehicle. This approach aims to replace traditional capacitive sensors due to both financial and functional advantages. Capacitive sensors are notably susceptible to spoofing attempts using objects such as legs, fruits or cans, which compromises their reliability (see Figure 25). Moreover, these sensors cannot distinguish whether the hands on the steering wheel belong to the driver, a limitation that this camera-based system seeks to overcome. Additionally, this system is capable to distinguish between a hand that touches the steering wheel with or without controlling it (see Figure 27). By leveraging advanced image processing techniques, the HandsOn Steering Wheel Detection system enhances both the security and accuracy of driver monitoring, ensuring a safer and more efficient driving experience. In the current state the system operates with an accuracy of 91,6% (see Figure 28)

FIGURE 25 EXAMPLES FOR SPOOFING ATTEMPTS ON CAPACITIVE SENSORS

FIGURE 26 EXAMPLE OF "HANDSON" CLASSIFICATION

FIGURE 27 EXAMPLE OF "HANDSOFF" CLASSIFICATION WHILE STEERING WHEEL IS TOUCHED

Ground Truth	Not in Control	5250 (90,81 %)	531 (9,19 %)
	In Control	619 (7,88 %)	7234 (92,12 %)
		Not in Control	In Control
		Prediction	

FIGURE 28 HANDSON DETECTION OVERALL ACCURACY OF 91,6%

2.8. Cognitive Workload estimation

The aim of this module is to estimate the driver workload based on EEG physiological signals. This module has as output two workload levels: high workload levels from low ones. To have more information's related to the detailed description of the design approach of this module see the deliverable D3.1.

The decision process is handled by a machine learning model. In order to train it, signals were collected during experiments. Subjects were asked to perform low-demand tasks, then high-demand tasks. Once the signals have been recorded, some relevant features are extracted from them. They consist of spectral energy on EEG frequency bands. Once features are extracted, they are eventually used to feed the model.

The delivered module consists of an application based on a python library named Streamlit. It consists of an interface allowing to visualize live signals with the corresponding model-calculated cognitive workload level. A tab also provides a tool to calibrate the module on a specific person, which results in an increase in model performance.

FIGURE 29: VISUALISATION OF COGNITIVE LOAD ESTIMATION

2.9. Seat occupancy and health monitoring

A phased array radar sensor is used inside the vehicle in order to detect and classify the passengers as adults, children and infants. The radar sensor is placed on the driver's armrest, between the driver and co-driver as displayed in the Figure 30.

FIGURE 30: SENSOR POSITION AND VEHICLE USED FOR TESTING PURPOSES

The control of the phased array radar is still in progress and in the future, it is expected to provide also health signals as the respiration rate of the passengers. The current state has to do with the detection of point clouds that can be used for monitoring the occupancy of the vehicle (see Figure 31).

FIGURE 31 CAMERA VIDEO AND POINT CLOUD OF THE DETECTED PERSON

2.10. Situational Awareness

The Situational Awareness (SA) Module is designed to evaluate the driver's awareness in real time, serving as a critical component of the driver monitoring system. The module continuously assesses how well a driver's attention aligns with the demands of dynamic traffic scenarios. Currently the model is developed specifically for the lane change / overtake manoeuvre.

The basic principle of the module is estimating the SA per Area of Interest (Aoi). Seven Aois have been defined:

1. Left window
2. Left mirror
3. Front screen
4. Dashboard
5. Rearview mirror
6. Right mirror
7. Right window

Per Aoi a buffer is defined that 'fills up' when the driver looks into this area and 'empties' when the driver is not looking in this specific area. Each Aoi-buffer can have a different increase/decrease rate.

2.10.1. Design and Development Process

In order to find out how SA is related to gaze behaviour, an experiment was performed in the TNO driving simulator (see Figure 32).

FIGURE 32 IMPRESSION TNO DRIVING SIMULATOR EXPERIMENT

In this experiment, the participants drove on a highway, where they had to overtake slower driving traffic on the right lane. The gaze of the participants was recorded by gaze tracker instruments and the SA was assessed by pausing the simulation at specific moments relative to the slow driving vehicle and let the participants fill in a so-called SAGAT questionnaire (Situation Awareness Global Assessment Technique by Endsley³). This is a well-known specialised questionnaire designed to capture the situational awareness of an operator, as usually, this is not directly measurable.

To force different levels of SA of the participants, half of the group of participants had to perform an additional, visually distracting task during the experiment. Additionally, the amount of traffic in the faster lane was manipulated as well as the speed limit, to make the driving scene more dynamic. In total 38 participants completed the full experiment.

The SAGAT questionnaire consisted of 15 questions regarding their environment and their own position and speed. Every time the driving simulator was paused, participants had to answer 7 of those questions. The first question was always question A ("In which lane are you driving (left/right)?")

³ M. R. Endsley, "Situation awareness global assessment technique (SAGAT)," Proceedings of the IEEE 1988 National Aerospace and Electronics Conference, Dayton, OH, USA, 1988, pp. 789-795 vol.3, doi: 10.1109/NAECON.1988.19509

and the second question was always question B (“In which fields are other vehicles?”). The fields related to this question are shown in Figure 33. After these 2 questions there came 4 (out of 8: C-J) questions about the surrounding vehicles (for the vehicles by the participant indicated in question B) and the drivers’ own position and speed. The questionnaire ended with one question about the environment (out of 5: M-Q).

FIGURE 33: FIELDS AROUND THE VEHICLE WHERE OTHER VEHICLES WERE LOCATED (FROM QUESTIONNAIRE)

The information needed to answer questions related to field 4 and 5 (see Figure 33) needed to be perceived from the mirrors. If the simulator paused when the participant drove in the right lane, so before the lane change, gaze behavior in the rearview mirror was related to field 5-questions and gaze behavior in the left outside mirror was related to field 4-questions.

Question B (“In which fields are other vehicles?”) was answered by all participants in all pauses. However, since answers to question B were hard to interpret when question A (“In which lane are you driving (left/right)?”) was answered incorrectly, all answers where question A was incorrect were excluded from analysis. Since it only made sense to analyze the questions answers of question C-J (details about the vehicles in the different fields) when B was answered correctly and there actually was a vehicle present in simulation, all answers where this was not the case were removed from the analysis. The number of samples of questions C-J was too low to allow for separate question analysis. A way to combine the answers to allow for analysis of the questions as a whole was out of scope for this deliverable.’

2.10.2. Results of the experiment

Figure 34 shows the proportion of time participants fixated on an Area of Interest (AoI) with and without secondary task performed on a tablet attached to the center console. The absence of fixations shows that the tablet had no function during the drive in the condition without secondary task. The figure shows that performing the secondary task, and thereby the increase in fixations on the tablet, had mainly an effect on decreasing windshield fixations and rearview mirror (RVM) usage. Left mirror usage was less influenced by secondary task conditions.

FIGURE 34 PROPORTION OF TIME SPENT FIXATING ON AN AOI WITH AND WITHOUT SECONDARY TASK

Statistical analysis over all pauses shows that the secondary task had a negative effect on fixation duration during the last 10 seconds before the pause in the rearview mirror ($F(1,325) = 15.325, p < 0.001$) and through the windscreen ($F(1,325) = 31.99, p < 0.001$), but not on fixation duration in the left outer mirror ($F(1,325) = 0.11, p = 0.74$).

Figure 35 shows the percentage of question B4 (question about vehicle position in field 4) answered correctly while driving in the right lane versus the fixation frequency (left) and fixation duration (right) in the left mirror (LM) before the lane change in the last 10s before the pause, per pause. Red crosses indicate the results with secondary task and the blue crosses indicate the results without secondary task. The cross size indicates the amount of answers per fixation frequency. Participants who performed the secondary task while driving answered the B4 question (about vehicle position in field 4) correctly more often when they looked more often and/or longer in the left mirror. In contrast, there was no systematic relationship between viewing behavior and correct answers for the participants who did not have to perform the secondary task. This was confirmed by a significant interaction effect of secondary task condition and the two gaze variables (fixation frequency ($F(1,76) = 7.04, p = 0.01$) and duration ($F(1,76) = 4.7, p = 0.03$)).

FIGURE 35 PERCENTAGE OF QUESTION B4 ANSWERED CORRECTLY VERSUS FIXATION FREQUENCY (LEFT) AND FIXATION DURATION (RIGHT).

We did not find any relation between answers to question B5 and rearview mirror fixations or secondary task. We also did not find any relation between the detailed questions about the surrounding vehicles and mirror gaze behaviour.

2.10.3. Discussion and conclusion

In the secondary task condition, we found a clear systematic relation between gaze behavior in the left mirror and the percentage of question B4 answered correctly. Participants in this condition showed to have a higher SA behind them on the left lane, when they used their left mirror more often and for a longer period of time. These results can be used as a basis to estimate SA for lane changes in Demo 3. The implementation of the SA module will make use of the AttenD2.0 buffer model as a basis. Alternatively, we could estimate parameters of a buffer model on distraction as defined by Euro NCAP ⁴.

The results don't show an effect for the participants who did not perform the secondary task. These drivers have more time to look around and therefore the possibility that these participants used their mirrors before the 10s time period was higher. The scene did not change much during the drive and therefore looks in the mirror before this 10s time period could be sufficient to answer question B4. However, further research is needed to find out if this is indeed the case in the condition without secondary task.

SAGAT is widely used and accepted as a measure of SA; however, not all aspects of SA may concern explicit knowledge (often more implicit or automated). The lane in which the participant was driving is a good example hereof and is not something a normal driver is explicitly aware about.

⁴ [Euro NCAP Assessment Protocol - SA Safe Driving - v10.0.2](https://cdn.euroncap.com/media/67892/euro-ncap-assessment-protocol-sa-safe-driving-v1001.pdf)
<https://cdn.euroncap.com/media/67892/euro-ncap-assessment-protocol-sa-safe-driving-v1001.pdf>

This experiment was performed in a driving simulator with little risk. Gaze behavior in a driving simulator could be different from gaze behavior in real traffic. Therefore, validation during real driving is necessary.

2.10.4. Required SA

The actual SA of the driver, should be compared to the required SA, as only then, mismatches may appear and measures can be taken to counteract (e.g. through an HMI). To evaluate the required SA for the overtake scenario, first a task analysis was done. This was then used to perform a risk analysis per defined subtask. The result of this risk analysis has been used to determine the required SA per Aol.

Additionally, the SA Module utilizes SCANeR simulation data to evaluate the traffic situation in real time. This integration allows the module to dynamically determine which Aols are relevant based on the current driving context, see e.g. Figure 36.

FIGURE 36: FLOW CHART OF THE OVERTAKING PROCESS (HIGH LEVEL)

Key inputs and metrics include:

- Glance Fixation in Areas of Interest (Aols): The event that a driver is looking at specific regions, such as front screen, mirrors, dashboard, etc.
- Surrounding vehicle information: position and speed of surrounding vehicles

2.10.5. Integration with Other Modules

The SA Module integrates inputs from multiple sources:

- The **Gaze Region Module**, which tracks the driver's real-time gaze and provides information about where they are looking and whether gaze can be categorized as fixation, saccade or blink.
- The **SCANeR simulation platform**, which supplies contextual traffic data, such as surrounding vehicle positions, ego vehicle state and driver inputs.

This combination of gaze data and traffic context enables the module to evaluate not only where the driver is looking but also whether their focus is appropriate for the current driving situation (with a focus on overtaking/lane changing).

2.10.6. Functionality and Outputs

The SA Module operates by comparing:

1. **Estimated Awareness:** The driver's estimated SA, as derived from gaze data.
2. **Required Awareness:** The focus areas relevant to the current traffic situation, as identified using SCANeR data.

Using this comparison, the module:

- **Assesses Situational Awareness:** Determines the alignment between the driver's focus and the demands of the environment.

2.10.7. Impact and Importance

The Situational Awareness Module is a cornerstone of the driver monitoring system, offering a comprehensive evaluation of driver behavior and awareness. By integrating gaze data, SCANeR traffic context, and advanced modelling techniques, the module ensures identification of relevant Aols and provides real-time insights into the driver's situational awareness.

This approach significantly enhances safety in semi-autonomous and assisted driving systems by proactively detecting risks and helps improve driver engagement, ultimately contributing to a more reliable and adaptive driving experience.

2.11. Risk Assessment

The Risk Assessment (RA) Module is developed to analyze inputs from the simulator and vehicle sensors to evaluate the environment and identify the safest course of action for the autonomous vehicle. This module is designed to function in real time, ensuring safety and reliability even in complex or unpredictable driving scenarios.

2.11.1. Design and Development Process

The RA Module leverages data collected from both the simulator and on-board vehicle sensors to create a comprehensive understanding of the vehicle's surroundings and operational context. It calculates thousands of potential scenarios and evaluates the possible reactions of the vehicle to each situation.

Key considerations include:

- **Obstacle Locations:** Determining the position and trajectory of nearby dynamic objects, including other vehicles and pedestrians.
- **Vehicle Speed and Dynamics:** Analysing the current speed, acceleration, and handling capabilities of the vehicle.
- **Consequences of collision:** Potential collision scenarios are analysed and a severity for each road user and collision type is assigned.

The module is derived from a stochastic risk measure, treating risk as the expected severity of a risk inducing event, e.g. a collision. The uncertainty is captured in the prediction of the kinematic variables of other road users, and such is used to characterize Gaussian probability density functions. The probability density functions are then integrated over the set of possible collisions. Such that yields the expected severity of a collision. A stochastic model predictive path-following controller is then used to derive a vehicle trajectory balancing risk with travel efficiency. Such yields an optimal trajectory.

2.11.2. Functionality and Outputs

The RA Module performs the following core functions:

1. **Risk Evaluation:** Continuously assesses the level of risk associated with the current situation by analysing the vehicle's position, surroundings, and movement patterns of nearby objects.
2. **Scenario Analysis:** Calculates thousands of potential outcomes for a given situation by simulating various vehicle actions, such as braking, accelerating, or steering adjustments.
3. **Optimal Trajectory:** Identifies the trajectory or action that minimizes risk while maintaining efficiency and occupant comfort.

The module then provides recommended actions to the autonomous driving system, such as adjusting speed, changing lanes, or performing evasive manoeuvres, ensuring that safety is always the top priority. In Demonstrator 3, RA module will provide a risk value for Decision-Making (DM) module.

Figure 37 showcases the blue ego vehicle overtaking the red object vehicle under varying uncertainties around the red vehicle's future trajectory. Note that the shapes of both road users are approximated by three circles each, which is also depicted in the figure.

FIGURE 37: OVERTAKING SCENARIO UNDER RISK OPTIMIZATION.

2.11.3. Integration with Other Modules

The RA module works in conjunction with other system components, such as:

- The **Decision-Making module**, RA module informs the DM module about the risk percentage.
- The **SCANeR simulation platform**, from which RA uses simulation data.

2.11.4. Impact and Importance

The Risk Assessment module is one of the vital components of the autonomous vehicle system, enabling real-time evaluation of potential hazards and ensuring the vehicle can respond appropriately to changing conditions. Its ability to analyse thousands of scenarios and recommend actions enhances the system's robustness and reliability.

The RA Module ensures that decisions are data-driven and optimized for occupant safety. This approach could significantly reduce the likelihood of accidents, making it a cornerstone of the project's mission to develop safe, adaptive, and intelligent autonomous driving systems.

2.12. Decision-Making Module

The Decision-Making Module (DMM) plays a crucial role in determining whether the driver is ready to take control of the vehicle from the autonomous system. By evaluating multiple inputs and integrating them into a cohesive readiness assessment, the module supports safe transitions between autonomous and manual driving.

2.12.1. Design and Development Process

Inputs

The DMM integrates data from multiple system components to ensure a holistic readiness assessment:

- **Driver Health:** Physiological data indicating fatigue or impairment.

- **Situational Awareness:** Output from the SA Module, which provides information about the driver's attentiveness and focus.
- **Cognitive Workload:** Measures of the mental demands on the driver in the current context.
- **Hands On/Off Status:** Data from steering wheel sensors indicating whether the driver is physically interacting with the vehicle.
- **Risk Assessment:** Output from the RA Module, detailing the level of risk in the current driving situation.

Dynamic Input Assessment

The DMM evaluates multiple inputs to gauge their relevance and urgency in decision-making. These inputs are categorized into **higher**, and **lower priority**, depending on their significance for decision making

- **Higher Priority Inputs:** These are critical, requiring immediate action to ensure safety.
 - **Example:** Driver impairment, such as health emergencies.
 - **Action:** The vehicle assumes full control immediately, executing safety protocols like an emergency stop if necessary.
- **Lower Priority Inputs:** These inputs encompass scenarios requiring timely but not urgent intervention, such as navigating a highway exit, or minor factors like distractions or secondary behaviours that impact driving decisions.
 - **Examples:** Cognitive load, or driver's gaze region, or slight multitasking.
 - **Action:** The DMM evaluates the driver's capacity to safely assume control, facilitating a smooth transition when feasible, or decides to maintain autonomous operation, ensuring all decisions consider the overall driving context.

Control Transition Scenarios:

The DMM is designed to handle Vehicle-to-Driver (V2D) and Driver-to-Vehicle (D2V) transitions with precision, ensuring safety and seamless interaction in both higher and lower priority scenarios.

Vehicle-to-Driver (V2D):

- **Higher Priority Scenarios:** The DMM transfers control only if the driver is deemed fit to respond effectively. If the driver is unfit, the vehicle executes pre-emptive safety measures, such as an emergency stop.
- **Lower Priority Scenarios:** For routine situations, the DMM evaluates all inputs to determine whether to maintain autonomous control or engage the driver. An interactive Human-Machine Interface (iHMI) keeps the driver informed and prepared for the transition.

Driver-to-Vehicle (D2V):

- **Higher Priority Scenarios:** During manual driving, if the system detects imminent risks requiring autonomous intervention, the DMM seamlessly assumes control to ensure safety.

- **Lower Priority Scenarios:** In less critical situations, the DMM evaluates inputs to decide whether to intervene or allow the driver to retain control, ensuring decisions are aligned with the overall driving context.

Fuzzy Logic Approach

Although a machine learning model could theoretically be used to predict driver readiness, the lack of comprehensive datasets encompassing all these diverse inputs required the adoption of an alternative approach. The DMM employs fuzzy logic, which is particularly effective for handling uncertain and imprecise data.

Fuzzy logic allows the DMM to evaluate nuanced inputs without rigid thresholds. For example, situational awareness scores of 80 and 85 may have similar implications for readiness, and fuzzy logic enables the module to process such subtle variations effectively.

The fuzzy logic approach for Transition of Control (ToC) scenario is shown in Figure 38.

FIGURE 38: DECISION-MAKING MODULE USING FUZZY LOGIC APPROACH FOR TRANSITION OF CONTROL SCENARIO

Outputs

The module produces the following outputs:

1. **Driver Readiness Level:** A real-time evaluation of whether the driver is prepared to take control.
2. **Rate and Direction of Readiness Change:** Insights into how the driver's readiness is evolving over time (e.g., improving, deteriorating).
3. **Estimated Time to High Readiness:** A prediction of how long it will take for the driver to reach a state of full readiness, if not already there.

Driver readiness provides a probabilistic output to quantify its confidence in the driver's ability to take control:

- **High Probability (90%+):** Indicates strong confidence in the driver's readiness. The DMM initiates a transfer with minimal delay.
- **Medium Probability (50-90%):** Reflects moderate confidence. The system transitions cautiously, maintaining vigilance.
- **Low Probability (<50%):** Suggests uncertainty. The vehicle retains control while continuously monitoring inputs.

Impact and Importance

The Decision-Making Module is a key enabler of safe and seamless control transitions in autonomous driving systems. Its use of fuzzy logic ensures robust performance even when inputs are uncertain or lack well-defined boundaries.

By evaluating readiness in real time and providing actionable outputs, the DMM supports adaptive and context-aware decision-making, significantly enhancing the safety and reliability of autonomous systems. Its ability to handle complex, multidimensional inputs sets it apart as a sophisticated and vital component of the project.

2.13. Transition of Control

In this project, the **Transition of Control (ToC) Module** is designed to manage the seamless and safe handover of control between the driver and the autonomous driving system. By ensuring that transitions occur smoothly and under appropriate conditions, the module enhances the safety, comfort, and situational awareness of both the driver and the vehicle.

Goals and Impact

The ToC Module aims to:

- **Ensure Safety:** By carefully evaluating readiness and system conditions, it minimizes risks during transitions.
- **Enhance Comfort:** Gradual transitions, when possible, prevent abrupt changes that could disorient or inconvenience the driver.
- **Maintain Situational Awareness:** Throughout the process, the module ensures that the driver remains informed and engaged.

Design and Functionality

The ToC Module relies on inputs from the **Decision-Making Module (DMM)** to guide the control handover process based on the driver's readiness and the current driving situation. Given that the vehicle operates in a highly automated mode, the ToC Module has higher authority in managing transitions of control. This ensures that the system can make decisions prioritizing safety and operational requirements, particularly in complex or time-critical situations.

Key functionalities include:

1. **Automated to Manual Transition:**
 - a. When the vehicle is operating in automated mode, the module continuously assesses the driver's readiness to take control.
 - b. Inputs such as the driver's readiness level and time to takeover determine whether the transition will be accepted by the system or not.
 - c. The module ensures that transitions occur only when the driver is sufficiently prepared, reducing the risk of errors during handover.
 - d. Apart from being attentive, the driver must actively press a button in the steering wheel to activate the manual mode.
2. **Manual to Autonomous Transition:**
 - a. While in manual mode, the driver can request a switch to automated control by pressing a designated button.
 - b. The ToC Module evaluates whether the vehicle is ready for autonomous mode by checking key conditions, such as system functionality, environmental factors, and situational context.
 - c. If all conditions are met, the module facilitates a smooth transition to automated mode.

Inputs and Dependencies

The module integrates data from multiple sources to ensure reliable performance:

- **Driver Readiness:** Provided by the Decision-Making Module, detailing whether the driver is ready to assume control.
- **Time to takeover:** When the automated mode is granted by the system and there is no incoming TOR expected, the system is more restrictive to allow the ToC. On the other side, if there is an incoming TOR, the system expects that the HMI will perform the corresponding warnings for the driver, allowing an intermediate level of driver readiness for the transition to manual.

Flowchart of the module

The transition module, shown in Figure 39 is designed to manage the switch between AD and manual driving modes based on driver readiness, button input, and the TTO. It ensures safety by continuously monitoring these inputs and enforcing specific conditions for a mode change.

The module begins operation when the TTO reaches 20 seconds, signaling the end of AD. Before this point, transitions are not permitted, and the system remains in AD mode. The primary inputs to the module are the driver's readiness level (scaled 0-100), the button press signal (binary), and the TTO value (0-20 seconds).

FIGURE 39 TRANSITION OF CONTROL FLOWCHART

When TTO drops below 20 seconds, the module evaluates the readiness level and the button press. For readiness levels above 80 (high readiness), the system transitions to manual mode only if the button is pressed. At readiness levels between 40 and 80 (medium readiness), the transition is allowed if the TTO is less than or equal to 10 seconds and the button is pressed. For readiness levels below 40 (low readiness), no transition occurs regardless of TTO or button press, maintaining the system in AD mode for safety.

If the TTO reaches 1 second, the module enforces an automatic transition to manual mode, regardless of readiness level or button press, ensuring the vehicle is safely controlled. The output of the module is a continuous value between 0 (manual) and 1 (AD), allowing for a smooth 2-second transition between modes by modulating the steering wheel torque signal.

The logic is designed to ensure that transitions occur only when conditions indicate that the driver is prepared to take over control, minimizing risks during critical moments of the transition.

Examples of the application

The Figure 40 illustrate the use cases of the ToC module. From top to bottom, each graph represents:

- **Time to takeover (TTO):** This graph shows the countdown as time progresses, indicating the remaining time before a takeover is required.
- **Button Signal:** This binary signal indicates whether the button on the steering wheel is pressed (1) or not (0). Driver readiness level: it is a continuous value from 0 (complete inattentive) to 100 (totally ready).
- **Driver Readiness Level:** A continuous value ranging from 0 (completely inattentive) to 100 (fully prepared to take control).
- **Steering Controller Output:** This signal controls the steering system's transition between modes. It decreases in an S-shaped curve to ensure a smooth handover.

Transition Prevention for Low Readiness

This figure demonstrates a scenario where the driver presses the button while their readiness level is low. In this case, the system prevents the transition, as the drivers may have pressed the button accidentally, without being attentive to the road or having their hands on the steering wheel. However, when the drivers' readiness level increases and they press the button again, the system activates the transition. Note that while this simulation shows a clean step in the readiness value, actual studies are expected to present more variable and gradual changes in this parameter.

Readiness and Time Sensitivity

In this example, the driver's readiness level is at an intermediate range. The first button press occurs when there is still ample time for the takeover ($TTO > 10$ s). In this case, the system requires the driver to be more attentive before allowing a transition. Later, the driver presses the button again, but this time the TTO is less than 10 seconds. Since the urgency is higher, the system allows the transition despite the intermediate readiness level.

Automatic Transition

This scenario highlights a situation where the driver does not press the button at all. In this case, the system enforces an automatic transition to manual control 1 second before the TTO reaches zero. This safety mechanism ensures that control is handed back to the driver before the autonomous system can no longer operate effectively.

FIGURE 40 SIMULATION OF THE MODULE: TRANSITION BEING DISABLED WHEN THE READINESS IS LOW

2.14. Fault-awareness module

The localization system is equipped with a fault awareness decision-making module, which oversees determining the reliability of the localization module output. This decision-making module is again based on fuzzy logic and uses the covariances from each of the localization sources, as well as from the output of the fault tolerant localization algorithm to determine the confidence that can be given to the localization output. It is composed of three possible states: "Normal Operation" is assigned when the localization output is dependable and can be used indefinitely for operating the vehicle. In "Degraded Operation" mode, the performance and the accuracy has been decreased, but is still accurate enough to maintain the vehicle operation at reduced speeds, and during a limited time. Finally, "Emergency" represents a localization that is not precise enough for autonomous operation and can lead to a dangerous situation.

The fuzzy logic rules are defined as follow:

- The operation mode must be **normal** if the fault tolerant localization covariance and any localization source covariance are “low”.
- The operation mode must be **degraded** if the fault tolerant localization covariance is “low”, but there is not any localization source covariance that is “low”.
- The operation mode must be **degraded** if the fault tolerant localization covariance is “medium” and there is at least a localization source covariance that is not “high”.
- The operation mode must be **emergency** if the fault tolerant localization covariance is “medium” but all the localization sources covariances are “high”.
- The operation mode must be **emergency** if the fault tolerant localization covariance is “high”.

The defined rules form a six-dimensional control surface, which cannot be plotted on a graph. For illustration purposes, Figure 41 represents the control surface at different operation points of the map-based LiDAR localization, the LiDAR odometry and the I2V-based localization. Thus, the GNSS and the EKF (Fault tolerant localization) covariances are the only variables.

FIGURE 41. DECISION-MAKING MODULE FOR FAULT-AWARENESS LOCALIZATION. CONTROL SURFACES AT DIFFERENT OPERATION POINTS.

3. Conclusions

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the development of algorithms for the Occupant Monitoring Systems (OMS) technologies, from Gaze estimation, distraction and cognitive load detection, hands on/off detection, occupancy estimation, situational awareness, among others. Additionally, it covers other algorithms necessary for L2 to L3 transition, such as risk assessment, transition of control and decision-making modules. Every module was documented with several visual proof and descriptions of how these systems work.

This deliverable also offers details of integration into different testing vehicles and facilities, and into the IRSTX simulator for Demonstrator 3. This progress signifies the commitment of Aware2All partners to delivering high-quality, integrated prototypes that can be demonstrated at various locations.

